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Non-destructive Dendrochronology: The Effect of Conservation Agents on Tree-ring Measurements in Archaeological Oak with Micro-computed Tomography*

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ABSTRACT

The effect of different conservation methods on non-destructive dendrochronology with micro-computed tomography (μ CT) of waterlogged archaeological wood (WAW) was assessed. To this end, oak samples were conserved with alcohol-ether-resin, Kauramin 800[®], lactitol/trehalose, saccharose, silicone oil and different polyethylene glycol (PEG) treatments with subsequent freeze-drying. Tree-ring measurements were compared with respect to the number of rings and the mean ring width using (a) an analog linear measuring table and (b) the digital μ CT. Overall, the measurements in the μ CT data agreed very well with the corresponding microscopic measurements. It was possible in all cases to recognize the rings in the samples with μ CT. A dendrochronological cross dating with regional absolutely dated oak ring width chronologies was successful. However, the varying influence of conservation agents on the quality of the μ CT data were also evident. To quantify this influence, the contrast in the μ CT data were calculated using gray-scale profiles. An influence on the contrast in the μ CT data were detectable for all conservation agents. The contrast is especially reduced due to conservation methods using lactitol/trehalose, PEG, saccharose and silicone oil. Overall, the experiments confirm, though, that μ CT is a powerful and accurate tool for dendrochronology of conserved archaeological oak objects.

RÉSUMÉ

L'effet de différents traitements de conservation-restauration sur la dendrochronologie non destructive avec micro-tomographie assistée par ordinateur (μ CT) réalisée sur des bois archéologiques gorgés d'eau a été évalué. Pour cela, des échantillons de chêne ont reçu des traitements par alcool-éther-résine, Kauramin 800, lactitol/tréhalose, saccharose, huile de silicone et différents polyéthylène glycols (PEG) suivis d'une lyophilisation. Les mesures de cernes ont été comparées en prenant en compte le nombre de cernes et la largeur de cerne moyenne, en utilisant (a) un tableau de mesure linéaire analogique et (b) la μ CT numérique. De manière générale, les mesures obtenues par μ CT coïncidaient très bien avec les mesures microscopiques correspondantes. Il a été possible dans tous les cas d'identifier les cernes des échantillons grâce à la μ CT. Une datation par dendrochronologie croisée avec des chronologies de largeur de cernes faites sur chêne local daté de manière absolue a été probante. Cependant, l'influence variable des produits de conservation-restauration sur la qualité des données de la μ CT a également été mise en évidence. Afin de quantifier cette influence, les contrastes dans les données de la μ CT ont été calculés à l'aide d'échelles de valeurs de gris. Une influence sur le contraste dans les données de la μ CT a été détectée pour l'ensemble des produits de conservation-restauration testés. Ce contraste est particulièrement réduit par les traitements au lactitol/tréhalose, PEG, saccharose et huile de silicone. Les expériences menées confirment néanmoins que la μ CT est un outil performant et précis pour la dendrochronologie d'objets archéologiques en chêne ayant reçu des traitements de conservation-restauration. *Traduit par Claire Cuyaubère.*

RESUMO

Foi avaliado o efeito de diferentes métodos de conservação na dendrocronologia não destrutiva com microtomografia computadorizada (μ CT) de madeira arqueológica encharcada (MAE). Para tanto, amostras de carvalho foram conservadas com álcool-éter-resina, Kauramin 800, lactitol/trealose, sacarose, óleo de silicone e diferentes tratamentos com polietilenoglicol (PEG) com

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posterior liofilização. As medições dos anéis das árvores foram comparadas com relação ao número de anéis e à largura média dos anéis usando (a) uma mesa de medição linear analógica e (b) a μ CT digital. No geral, as medições nos dados de μ CT coincidiram muito bem com as medições microscópicas correspondentes. Foi possível em todos os casos reconhecer os anéis nas amostras com μ CT. Uma datação cruzada dendrocronológica com cronologias regionais de largura de anel de carvalho completamente datadas foi bem-sucedida. No entanto, a variação da influência dos agentes de conservação na qualidade dos dados de μ CT também foi evidente. Para quantificar essa influência, o contraste dos dados de μ CT foi calculado usando perfis em escala de cinza. Uma influência no contraste dos dados de μ CT foi detectada para todos os agentes de conservação. O contraste é especialmente reduzido em decorrência do uso de métodos de conservação que utilizam lactitol/trealose, PEG, sacarose e óleo de silicone. No geral, os experimentos confirmam, porém, que a μ CT é uma ferramenta poderosa e precisa para a dendrocronologia de objetos arqueológicos de carvalho conservados. *Traduzido por Carla Coelho.*

RESUMEN

Se evaluó el efecto de los diferentes métodos de conservación de madera arqueológica saturada con agua en la dendrocronología no destructiva con tomografía micro computarizada (μ TC). Para este propósito, muestras de roble fueron conservadas con resina alcohol-éter, Kauramin 800®, lactitol/micosa, sacarosa, aceite de silicona y diferentes tratamientos de polietilenglicol (PEG) con el subsecuente liofilizado. Las mediciones de los anillos de crecimiento fueron comparadas con el número de anillos y el espesor medio de anillo, usando (a) una tabla de medida análoga linear y (b) un medidor digital μ TC. En términos generales, las mediciones obtenidas por μ TC concordaron bastante bien con las mediciones microscópicas correspondientes. Fue posible en todos los casos reconocer los anillos de crecimiento en las muestras usando μ TC. Fue así mismo exitosa una datación dendrocronológica cruzada con dataciones regionales absolutas del espesor de los anillos de crecimiento del roble. Pese a ello, la influencia variable de los productos de conservación en la calidad de los datos por μ TC resultó igualmente evidente. Para cuantificar esta influencia, el contraste en los datos de μ TC fue calculado usando unos perfiles de escala de grises. Una influencia en el contraste de los datos μ TC fue detectable para todos los agentes de conservación. El contraste se redujo particularmente con los métodos de conservación en los que se usaron lactitol/micosa, PEG, sacarosa y aceite de silicona. En general, los experimentos confirman que la μ TC es una herramienta poderosa y precisa para la dendrocronología de objetos arqueológicos de roble conservados. *Traducción: David Cohen y Soledad Tancoff; revisión: Amparo Rueda e Irene Delaveris.*

1. Introduction

Archaeological objects that were crafted from wood are preserved in the temperate zone mainly under waterlogged and anoxic conditions, where microbial decay is slowed down, and the wood structure is more or less completely filled with water. Depending on the degree of degradation, waterlogged archaeological wood (WAW) may collapse and shrink when it is allowed to dry in an uncontrolled manner after excavation, leading to a total loss of the object's original shape and its information. A variety of methods and conservation agents have been tested for the conservation of WAW and several comparative studies aimed to compare the efficiency of the treatment methods (Christensen, Kutzke, and Hansen 2012; Walsh et al. 2014, 2017; Broda and Hill 2021; Stelzner et al. 2022).

As wooden objects have a long history in human development and technological evolution, they bear essential information in archaeological research. As plants adapt to environmental conditions throughout their lives and store this information in their tissue, analysis of the wood materials allow reconstruction of the living conditions of the trees. Archaeological wood offers an archive for interdisciplinary research.

Ecological, economic, vegetation-historical, climatic and cultural-historical questions can be addressed. Furthermore, dendrochronology is a widespread, reliable, and very accurate method for dating archaeological wooden finds and, therefore, an essential tool for archaeological research (Schweingruber 2001; Baillie 2002; Hughes 2002; Speer 2010; Billamboz 2014). When the outermost tree ring under the bark (wane edge) has been preserved, both the felling date and the felling season can be determined (Sass-Klaassen, Vernimmen, and Baittinger 2008). The width of the tree rings is usually measured on the cross-section with an accuracy of 1/100 mm (Westphal and Heußner 2016). For conventional dendrochronological dating, the artifact has to be sawn or drilled with an increment borer, which is contrary to the aim of conservation to preserve the object unaltered and as a whole. Also, preparing the cross-sectional surface with a razor blade for a dendrochronological dating is an invasive procedure on an artifact (Sass and Eckstein 1994; Kuniholm 2001; Bräker 2002; Westphal and Heußner 2016).

Among the non-destructive methods currently available, X-ray computed tomography (CT) is an appropriate technique that allows inspection of the entire volume of the sample at different spatial resolutions (Withers

et al. 2021). The technique provides for archaeological sciences very promising information in the field of dendroarchaeology, including conservation science (Stelzner et al. 2021, 2022). In addition to being non-invasive, it also requires almost no sample preparation and enables both qualitative and quantitative three-dimensional (3D) tree-ring analysis (Van den Bulcke et al. 2014; Martinez-Garcia et al. 2021, 2022). For these reasons, CT has made great progress as a leading non-destructive microscopic technique in the field of dendrochronology.

First attempts in non-destructive dendrochronological dating based on CT images were pursued in the 1980s (Onoe et al. 1984). However, non-destructive analysis and successful dating of wood samples only became feasible with the development of industrial μ CT with small focal spot size X-ray tubes and high-resolution detectors, which greatly improved the spatial resolution of X-ray CT systems (Okochi, Fujii, and Mitsutani 2007). For instance, the oak figures from Fellbach-Schmidten were dated to 127 ± 10 BCE (Keefer et al. 2006) and the oak figure from Eschenz to 9 ± 10 BCE (Belz et al. 2008). In both cases the sapwood was present on the oak. The felling date can then be narrowed down to 20 years which is written as the date ± 10 (Hollstein 1980). Grabner et al. (2007, 2009) managed dating archaeological objects from the archaeological site Hallstatt made of fir (835 BCE, no waney edge), beech (1378 BCE, waney edge dating) and silver fir (1362 BCE, no information about the waney edge). Furthermore, the dendrochronology of wood in blocks of soil was explored with μ CT (Stelzner and Million 2015), enabling the dating of fragments of oak (CE 500, no waney edge). Kastner et al. (2007), Grabner et al. (2007, 2009), Bill et al. (2012) and Stelzner and Million (2015) in the same way, reported on the limits of the measurability of ring widths, as the image resolution depends on the object size.

A large-scale study on more than 90 oak objects confirms the potential of μ CT for non-destructive dendrochronological analysis, with only six objects remaining undated (Bill et al. 2012). However, an important factor affecting the validity of the results is the condition of the objects. The waterlogged finds examined by Bill et al. (2012) had been air-dried, because the measurements of the water-saturated timbers and of the samples impregnated with high-molecular polyethylene glycol (PEG) did not produce sufficient contrast for a determination of tree-ring widths. The problem of conserved WAW with regards to non-destructive dendrochronology was confirmed by Wiesner et al. (2016) in the case of a prehistoric wheel made of maple, which had been conserved with 40% PEG 2000 and freeze-dried. In

contrast, Daly and Ebert (2021) successfully dated a lid of an oak barrel from Odense, Denmark, conserved with 38% PEG 2000 and subsequently freeze-drying, to 1332 CE (no waney edge) based on 217 measured tree rings. Apart from this case, the figures from Eschenz (alcohol-ether-resin method) (Belz et al. 2008) and Fellbach-Schmidten, which had been conserved with obsolete materials like Lyofix (Keefer et al. 2006), no conserved archaeological objects have been dated so far by CT and therefore also Bill et al. (2012) recommend that further experiments should be carried out with CT and conserved wood for dendrochronology.

The principal aim of conservation is to bring an artifact into a condition of long-term chemical stability and to achieve a homogeneous mechanical stabilization of the structure. However, in the case of archaeological wood, treatment may impact the future non-destructive dendrochronological analyses with CT. Due the difficulty of analyzing archaeological wood in a wet condition the question arises whether the structural information of the historical sources is still accessible and evaluable after conservation. Therefore, this study aimed to elucidate which common conservation method allows non-destructive dating with μ CT, and what influence these methods have on the visibility of the annual rings in the μ CT data. Since oak is the most important wood species for dendrochronology in Europe (Towner 2002; Haneca, Čufar, and Beeckman 2009), the conservation methods were carried out on oak samples. To check the results of the ring width measurements they were compared to analog conventional tree-ring measurements under the stereo microscope.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

For this study, conserved oak samples from the Roman period were available from the scientific reference collection of the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie in Mainz, Germany. The collection was built up between 2008 and 2011 by collecting large archaeological samples from central European sites, of different wood species and degrees of degradation. These samples were then divided into several equal sized samples and impregnated with the most established conservation methods at that time (Wittköpper et al. 2016; Stelzner et al. 2022). The samples were conserved at different institutions with their standard methods: alcohol-ether-resin (Bräker et al. 1979, Schmidt-Ott, André, and Bader 2022), melamine-formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) (Wittköpper 1998), lactitol/trehalose (Imazu and Morgós 2002), saccharose (Parrent 1985), silicone oil

(Smith 2003) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) with subsequent freeze-drying. PEG treatment followed either a one-step process with PEG 2000 (Jensen, Petersen, and Straetkvern 2011), two-step with PEG 400 and PEG 4000 (Cook and Grattan 1990) or three-step with PEG 400, PEG 1500 and PEG 4000 (www.rgzm.de/kur). The degree of degradation was determined by the maximum water content (U_{max}) in percent and the basic density in g/cm^3 (Stelzner et al. 2022). A detailed overview of the conservation methods and the samples is given on the project homepage (www.rgzm.de/kur). For the analyses in this study, the three largest oak (*Quercus robur*, *Q. petraea*) test series of the collection were selected in order to cover a high variety of methods (Table 1). This systematic collection of samples provides a unique chance to compare the structural differences of the conserved wood (Wittköpper et al. 2016; Stelzner et al. 2021, 2022). Each test series of the collection includes samples derived from the same object or context (same wood species and excavation site, similar state of preservation) that were conserved with the different treatments. Due to the different sizes of the objects, the number of samples varied. Therefore, not all test series contain all conservation methods.

The sample names in Table 1 indicates from which oak object and test series (Oa1, Oa2 and Oa3) the sample originates and with which conservation agent it was conserved. In addition, the KUR number is given in order to identify the sample in the database on the project homepage (www.rgzm.de/kur).

2.2. Micro-computed tomography

The tomographic analysis was performed on the in-house laboratory X-ray μ CT system (Diondo d2, Germany) at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts. An optimized setup and acquisition protocol for the μ CT measurements was developed for conserved wood. The measurements were conducted by setting the X-ray source (XWT-225 TCHE+ from X-ray works, Garbsen, Germany) in high power mode and choosing an operation voltage of 120 kV and a filament current of 167 μ A with a 1 mm aluminum filter. The wood samples were mounted in a sample holder and placed in the sample chamber. The sample was rotated 360° and measurements were performed in the continuous mode during the acquisition. The radiographical projections were recorded with a 4343 DX-I X-ray detector (Varex, Salt Lake City, U.S.A.), with a pixel size of 139 μ m. The distances between the X-ray source and the sample varied between 160 and 250 mm and between the X-ray source and the detector was 860 mm, giving a magnification between 3.4 and 5.4 and a nominal voxel size between 27 and 44 μ m. A total of 3000 projection images were acquired during the sample rotation of 360°. The resulting projections were converted into a 3D image stack of approx. 3000 \times 3000 \times 3000 voxels using the CERA reconstruction software based on the filtered back projection Feldkamp algorithm (Feldkamp, Davis, and Kress 1984) from Siemens. The achieved resolution of the μ CT measurements depends on the size of the samples (Stelzner and Million 2015). Table 1 provides an overview of

Table 1. Information on the conservation, condition, dimensions and μ CT resolution of the oak objects and samples.

Sample	KUR-No.	Object	Conservation method	U_{max} (%)	Basic density (g/cm^3)	Dimensions L, \varnothing (cm)	Resolution μ CT (μ m)
Oa1-Air	V10-02	Pile	Air dried	201	0.374	17, 7	32
Oa1-K800	V10-06	Pile	Kauramin 800	198	0.378	16, 7	32
Oa1-LaTr	V10-33	Pile	Lactitol/trehalose	160	0.441	15, 7	32
Oa1-PEG1	V10-29	Pile	PEG 2000	179	0.407	11, 7	32
Oa1-PEG2	V10-31	Pile	PEG 400, 4000	176	0.412	12, 7	32
Oa1-PEG3	V10-39	Pile	PEG 400, 1500, 4000	181	0.404	13, 7	32
Oa1-Sac	V10-03	Pile	Saccharose	163	0.435	14, 7	32
Oa2-Air	V16-15	Plank	Air dried	362	0.233	12, 16	33
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	Plank	Alcohol-Ether	175	0.414	12, 16	32
Oa2-K800	V16-25	Plank	Kauramin 800	228	0.339	12, 16	44
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	Plank	PEG 2000	189	0.391	12, 16	35
Oa2-PEG2	V16-32	Plank	PEG 400, 4000	237	0.329	12, 16	44
Oa2-PEG3	V16-36	Plank	PEG 400, 1500, 4000	188	0.393	12, 16	35
Oa2-Sac	V16-17	Plank	Saccharose	184	0.399	12, 16	35
Oa2-Sil	V16-13	Plank	Silicone oil	187	0.394	12, 16	32
Oa3-Air	V27-17	Branch	Air dried	577	0.155	12–14, 5–6	19
Oa3-AIEt	V27-40	Branch	Alcohol-Ether	527	0.168	12–14, 5–6	32
Oa3-K800	V27-07	Branch	Kauramin 800	646	0.140	12–14, 5–6	26
Oa3-LaTr	V27-30	Branch	Lactitol/trehalose	566	0.158	12–14, 5–6	26
Oa3-PEG1	V27-12	Branch	PEG 2000	691	0.132	12–14, 5–6	32
Oa3-PEG2	V27-02	Branch	PEG 400, 4000	578	0.155	12–14, 5–6	32
Oa3-PEG3	V27-01	Branch	PEG 400, 1500, 4000	557	0.160	12–14, 5–6	39
Oa3-Sac	V27-21	Branch	Saccharose	434	0.200	12–14, 5–6	26
Oa3-Sil	V27-10	Branch	Silicone oil	520	0.170	12–14, 5–6	26

Figure 1. Measurement radii of tree-ring widths, analog on the prepared surface of the sample conserved with saccharose from the first test series (Oa1-Sac).

Figure 2. Measurement radii of tree-ring widths in the μ CT data of the sample conserved with saccharose from the first test series (Oa1-Sac).

the samples, their size and the achieved resolution of the μ CT measurements.

2.3. Tree-ring width measurements

Ring width measurements in the image cross-sections of the μ CT data were performed with VGStudio Max 3.4©. For each sample two radii were measured. After μ CT measurement, the samples were prepared for the conventional analog manual measurements. For this purpose, the surface was leveled and polished with the aid of a geared eccentric sander (Festool, RO150FEQ). An ascending grit of 40, 80, 180, 400 and finally 800 was used for sanding the sample surfaces. Only in a few cases a preparation of the surface with a conventional razor blade was necessary. Subsequently, the annual ring widths were measured with a stereo microscope on a linear measuring table along two radii (Rinntech Lintab). For the validation of both measurements, the tree ring curves of each radius per sample of the analog and the μ CT measurement were compared to each other (Figures 1–3).

In the next step the number of rings of the analog and μ CT measurements were compared. In this way, it was checked whether all rings could be detected in the μ CT cross-sections. Additionally, the arithmetic mean of the tree-ring widths was calculated. With the purpose to get a ratio easy to compare and to interpret, the number of tree rings and the arithmetic mean of the ring width, the individual value for the digital measurement was subtracted from the analog, by achieving a calculated difference as a measure for the detection of divergences.

2.4. Irregularly shaped tree-ring width measurements

For samples exhibiting irregularly shaped rings (i.e., irregular annual growth), an alternative tree-ring width measurement approach based on image processing algorithms is used (Martinez-Garcia et al. 2021, 2022). From the μ CT image cross-section, the approach enables to detect first the pixels located along each annual ring (i.e., the ring pixels). Once recognized these pixels, their coordinates, (x,y), are extracted from the μ CT image cross-section. This data is then used to compute the distance between two consecutive rings, along the radial direction (i.e., along the line running from the pitch to the bark). Since these coordinates are points lying along the entire annual ring, the distance between two consecutive rings is calculated along a large number of radial directions (usually more than thousand directions are considered). Finally, the ring width distances obtained along all radial directions are averaged and its mean value is taken as the measure of the tree-ring width. In this way, the approach provides a more realistic tree-ring width estimate than considering only few radii in the measurement. All algorithms used were implemented in Python 3.7, supported by tools provided by the open-source image processing libraries scikit-image and OpenCV. This measuring method is applied here as an example to two samples of the branches with irregularly shaped tree ring of the third series of samples (Oa3): the sample conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Oa3-AIEt) and the sample conserved with silicone oil (Oa3-Sil).

2.5. Gray value analysis

To get information about the influence of the conserving agent on the visibility of the rings in the μ CT images the quality of the data were evaluated by calculating the contrast. For this purpose, the data were calibrated during import into VGStudio MAX 3.4 by

Figure 3. Tree ring curves of the measured radii from the different methods of the sample conserved with saccharose from the first test series in synchronous position (Oa1-Sac).

Figure 4. Gray value profile (50 mm) along one tree-ring widths measurement radius in the calibrated μ CT data of the sample conserved with saccharose from the first test series (Oa1-Sac).

Figure 5. μ CT cross-sections of the non-conserved sample from the first test series (Oa1-Air).

defining the background (air) and the most strongly absorbing part of the wood (e.g., medullary ray) to specific gray values. The distribution of the gray values possible with 16-bit data sets is 65535. Within the possible 65535 gray values, the background (air) was set to the gray value 10000 and the material (wood) to the gray value 50000 when calibrating the measurements. In μ CT data, gray value profiles were taken along the radii of the ring width measurements. The distances were equal for each test series and the profiles were taken without gaps or inclusions in the wood that might interfere with the result (Figure 4). The values were exported and the image contrast was calculated by dividing the difference of the maximum and

Table 2. Tree-ring width measurements.

Sample	KUR-No.	Number of rings on surface	Number of rings μ CT	Difference of rings	Difference in mean ring width (mm)	Smallest ring width (mm)
Oa1-Air	V10-02	37	37	0	-0.022	0.32
Oa1-K800	V10-06	80	80	0	-0.018	0.18
Oa1-LaTr	V10-33	59	64	+5 (μ CT)	-0.057	0.33
Oa1-PEG1	V10-29	79	82	+3 (μ CT)	+0.004	0.20
Oa1-PEG2	V10-31	75	81	+6 (μ CT)	+0.036	0.18
Oa1-PEG3	V10-39	80	82	+2 (μ CT)	-0.034	0.20
Oa1-Sac	V10-03	77	77	0	-0.011	0.18
Oa2-Air	V16-15	50	51	+1 (μ CT)	+0.076	0.91
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	69	69	0	+0.016	1.05
Oa2-K800	V16-25	121	121	0	+0.008	0.59
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	99	99	0	+0.003	0.64
Oa2-PEG2	V16-32	120	120	0	+0.002	0.50
Oa2-PEG3	V16-36	101	101	0	+0.022	0.79
Oa2-Sac	V16-17	95	95	0	-0.032	0.77
Oa2-Sil	V16-13	50	50	0	-0.010	1.34
Oa3-Air	V27-17	10	10	0	+0.037	0.46
Oa3-AIEt	V27-40	10	10	0	+0.126	0.87
Oa3-K800	V27-07	12	12	0	-0.151	0.47
Oa3-LaTr	V27-30	6	6	0	-0.010	1.76
Oa3-PEG1	V27-12	15	15	0	-0.087	0.45
Oa3-PEG2	V27-02	15	15	0	-0.020	0.56
Oa3-PEG3	V27-01	15	15	0	-0.030	0.72
Oa3-Sac	V27-21	14	14	0	+0.037	0.69
Oa3-Sil	V27-10	10	10	0	-0.018	1.18

minimum by the mean value of the gray value profiles (Peli 1990).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Tree-ring width measurements

In the first test series, the sample without conservation (Oa1-Air) illustrates the need for conservation. Figure 5 clearly shows how the heavily degraded areas of the sample have completely collapsed in the outer region. In contrast to the conserved samples, tree-ring widths can no longer be measured here. The inner areas of

the air-dried specimen are very well preserved. Though, no strong shrinkage and no collapse of the wood can be observed here.

The results of the ring width measurements show that in all conserved samples the rings could be captured on the basis of μ CT data. The resolution of 19–44 μ m achieved in the various measurements made it possible to detect ring widths down to the smallest ring width of 0.18 mm, regardless of the conservation method used. Moreover, in some cases it was possible to detect some rings at the end of the radii better with μ CT than with the conventional measurement method (Table 2). The reason for this is that the

Figure 6. Breaks and voids of the outer areas in the surface of the three-step PEG conserved sample of the first test series (Oa1-PEG3) (left) and μ CT cross-section of this part (right).

Figure 7. Degraded parts and smeared surface in the outer areas of the two-step PEG conserved sample of the first test series (Oa1-PEG2) (left) and μ CT cross-section of this part (right).

Figure 8. Difference between the arithmetic mean tree-ring widths from μ CT to analog measurement.

heavily degraded and partially erupted edge areas were in some cases better visible in the μ CT data than on the surface (Figure 6). The surface was also partially smeared by the conservation agent, as illustrated by the smooth area at the edge of the sample in Figure 7. In the μ CT data, the rings in these areas were more clearly visible in the axially slightly lower planes. Here, the μ CT data also allowed a broader inspection of ring widths in both horizontal and vertical dimension, in a 3D way, while the conventional measurement method is restricted to the cross-section which is cut physically only once.

To get an impression of the accuracy of the ring width measurements in the μ CT data the results were compared with the conventional measurements in term of the mean ring widths. Overall, the ring width measurements in the μ CT data agreed well with the microscopic measurements (Figure 8). The deviation

for all samples in the first two test series (Oa1 and Oa2) showed only minimal overall deviations of less than 0.1 mm. In terms of the tree-ring widths, this corresponds to a maximum deviation of approximately 5%. The larger deviations over 0.1 mm in the third test series (Oa3) can probably be explained by the more eccentric growth of the tree rings in the examined samples of an oak branch. Such irregular growth can be compensated for by the application of algorithms, which enable the analysis and measurement of entire rings as a result. Figure 9 shows a comparison of tree-ring widths measurements using a recently proposed entire-profile automated approach (Martinez-Garcia et al. 2021, 2022) and considering only two orthogonal radii using the VGStudio Max 3.4© software. The measurements were performed on image cross-sections of μ CT data obtained for samples conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Oa3-AlEt) and silicon

Figure 9. Average tree-ring widths computed over thousands of radii along the entire ring profile (automated approach) and over two arbitrarily chosen orthogonal radii (manual method) for wood samples conserved with (a) alcohol-ether-resin (Oa3-AIEt) and (b) silicone oil (Oa3-Sil). The detected ring positions used in the automated approach are highlighted in red. Annual rings are numbered starting from the center.

oil (Oa3-Sil) of the third test series. The results show that in both samples the agreement between manual and automated measurements are not good enough at some annual rings. For the sample Oa3-AIEt (Figure 9(a)), a deviation of 0.4 mm between both ring-width measurements was obtained at the third ring-width point (i.e., ring width measured between the rings No. 3 and 4 counted from the pith to the bark), whereas for the sample Oa3-Sil (Figure 9(b)), deviations between 0.4 and 0.6 mm were observed for ring-widths No. 2, 7, and 8. These results indicate that for irregularly shaped rings, ring width measurements along only two orthogonal radii are not always accurate enough and averaging over the entire ring profiles can provide a more realistic measurement.

On the basis of the measured annual rings the samples from the first test series (Oa1) could be dated

to 86 CE (with wany edge) and the samples of the second test series (Oa2) to 115 BCE.

Due to the small number of rings, no dendrochronological dating of the third series of samples (Oa3) was possible.

3.2. Visibility of rings in μ CT data

Overall, the annual rings were visible in the μ CT data of all samples. Differences were nevertheless obvious for the sample series themselves and for the different conservation agents. This was confirmed by the gray value profiles and the contrast calculated from them. Evident was the poorer contrast in the μ CT data of the third series of samples (Oa3). These differences in the test objects themselves can be explained to some extent with the condition of the wood. The more degraded

Figure 10. Deviation of the mean contrast in the μ CT data calculated from the gray value profiles of the two radii of the tree-ring measurements.

samples from the third test series (Oa3) show the lowest contrast. The trend of poorer contrast for more degraded areas in the sample is also seen in the other two series of samples (Oa1 and Oa2). Another explanation for the contrast reduction is that samples of the third series (Oa3) are taken from branches. Here, the pores of the early wood are less pronounced than those of the other two series of samples (Oa1 and Oa2), due to the tapering effect that is triggered by the distance to the soil floor (Koçillari et al. 2021).

When considering the different conservation methods, it is first noticeable that all of them have an influence on the contrast in the μ CT data. Thus, a decrease in contrast can be clearly determined for all conservation agents compared to the non-conserved samples. The highest contrast values after the measurements without any conservation agents are observed for the samples conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Figure 10).

Lactitol/trehalose treated samples and especially the ones treated with silicone oil had the lowest contrast values. The influence of conservation is most evident in the third series of samples (Oa3), where there is for example a clear difference between the sample conserved with alcohol-ether-resin (Oa3-AlEt) and the sample conserved with silicone oil (Oa3-Sil) (Figure 9). One explanation again could be the less pronounced pores of the early wood of the branches in this test series, which could be filled by the silicone oil, thus reducing the contrast of the measurement. The hypothesis that the conservation methods that tend to fill the pores of the wood lead to reduced contrast μ CT data seems to be plausible. This hypothesis is supported by the observations that full impregnation of oak with PEG as described by Bill et al. (2012) prevents the visualization of the rings using μ CT, whereas conservation

with PEG followed by freeze-drying still allows the ring analysis as described here and by Daly and Ebert (2021). In contrast, the rings of the maple wheel conserved with the same method by Wiesner et al. (2016) could not be visualized, which can be explained by the different wood species and the smaller pore size (Grabner, Salaberger, and Okochi 2009).

4. Conclusion

The results of this study confirm that all annual rings of the oak samples could be measured in the μ CT data. The tree-ring series of two test series (Oa1 and Oa2) could also be successfully cross dated to reference chronologies. The achieved resolution in the μ CT data were sufficient to detect all annual rings down to the smallest tree-ring width of 0.18 mm. The comparison with the conventional measurement confirmed the accuracy of the method. Furthermore, in some cases it was possible to obtain more rings at the outer areas of the samples using μ CT than conventional microscopy due to the three-dimensionality of the data. Moreover, annual rings in the strongly degraded and compressed areas of the samples could be better identified in the μ CT data and additional ring widths could be measured. Furthermore, the exemplary applied automatic measurement of tree-ring widths in the μ CT data provides more accurate results for irregularly shaped tree rings. The varying influence of the reviewed conservation agents on the quality of the μ CT data were also clearly evident. The best results could be achieved on the samples conserved with the alcohol-ether-resin method. However, an influence on the contrast in the μ CT data were detectable for all conservation agents compared to the non-conserved samples. This influence seems to be especially present for the conservation methods

using lactitol/trehalose, PEG, saccharose, and silicone oil, which have the property of filling the pores of the woods (Stelzner et al. 2023). Due to the large earlywood pore size of oak, the influence of the conservation methods investigated here seems to be small. So far, only conserved objects made of oak have been successfully dated using μ CT. Therefore, further research is needed on other wood species whose ring boundaries are less easy to recognize.

In conclusion, the experiments confirm that μ CT is a powerful and accurate tool for dendrochronology of conserved WAW. Successful ring width measurements are dependent on the quality of the μ CT data. Besides resolution, the contrast of the measurement is decisive for the visibility of the annual rings. To obtain sufficiently good μ CT data, however, certain factors must be considered: In addition to the equipment used (Bill et al. 2012; Křivánková, Nasswetrová, and Šmíra 2018; Mori, Kuhara, and Suzuki 2020), the quality determining factors also include the type of wood and the diameter of the object to be examined (Grabner et al. 2007, 2009; Stelzner and Million 2015). As this study shows, for conserved WAW finds, in addition to the above criteria, the condition of the wood and the conservation method used are relevant for successful dating using μ CT.

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